

The Beam Pipe Craftsmen

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Why We Want to Go	2
3	Aim of Our Experiment	2
4	Design	3
5	Experiment	4
5.1	Detector Setup	4
5.1.1	Timepix Setup: For pure 0.5 - 6 GeV beam (low intensity flux)	5
5.2	Experimental Methodology	5
5.2.1	1st Setup	5
5.2.2	2nd Setup	5
5.2.3	3rd Setup	6
5.2.4	4th Setup	6
5.2.5	5th Setup	7
6	Data Analysis	8
7	What do we hope to take away from this experience:	11
8	Outreach Activity	11
9	Acknowledgments	11
10	Appendix	12

Experimental Validation of Radially Adjustable Beam Pipe for Enhancing Beam Precision and Mitigating Off-axis Beam Loss Using Pure Electron Beam

1 Introduction

Particle accelerators use vacuum tubes to prevent air collision and ensure the beam remains focused. In most accelerator applications i.e. high energy density physics, heavy ion fusion etc., high intensity beams are transported through a conducting beam pipe. As charged particles flow inside the vacuum tube in, external forces are generated by image charge effects in a conducting pipe and self-fields produced by the beam itself [1], namely space charge effects, wake field[2] effects, image forces[3] due to conducting walls and resistive wall impedance. These forces alter the beam dynamics, causing tune shift, halo formation, and ultimately beam loss. These are governed by charge distribution, intensity, tube material and geometry.

Beam loss is a serious concern in efficiency of small-aperture focusing systems and transfer lines for accelerators design. Maintaining an optimum tube radius can reduce these effects. The beam tube is rigid, making the radius unchangeable, but beams of different energies and radius require different tube radius to ensure maximum focus. It has motivated us to design an radially adjustable beam pipe using **Iris Shutter Mechanism** to improve beam precision.

2 Why We Want to Go

We are a group of imaginative high school students from different backgrounds connected by our excitement for understanding our universe through physics. We know this challenge will push us beyond our knowledge, yet we are ready to step out for this adventure. We are optimistic about the application of our innovation in next-generation particle accelerators, particularly future colliders and medical applications. Hence, we are highly interested to visit CERN or DESY to materialize our design and test it, which is for us like a dream come true.

3 Aim of Our Experiment

We want to test the efficiency of our radially adjustable beam pipe using the 0.5 GeV - 6 GeV pure electron beam at CERN or DESY. Comparing the experimental results and the simulations we did using PYTHON for a perfectly conducting beam, we want to observe how well our design works, by which we can understand the difference between our adjustable pipe, whose surface is not perfectly round, and the typical beam pipe.

4 Design

Figure 1: *2d cross section of the beam pipe made using iris shutter mechanism*

We chose stainless steel as the base material of our vacuum pipe due to their flexibility, durability, suitable skin-depth, cost-effectiveness and lower conductivity. As the beam induces charge within the material, the material's resistance generates heat. So, we will use a $50 \mu\text{m}$ copper layer in the inner layer of the pipe to reduce resistance and heat. Our prototype pipe will be 12 m long,

Figure 2: *pipe's aperture at minimum radius*

Figure 3: *pipe's aperture at maximum radius*

with a 3 cm minimum radius (T9 Beamline beam radius is 2 cm, so we can observe the effect of wall with 3 cm radius) and 10 cm maximum radius, with more width than the skin depth of steel.

Using triangular blades made of stainless steel, we will ensure a non-overlapping shutter mechanism. Increasing the number of blades, N , will increase accuracy and reduce edge effects, likely mimicking a round beam pipe. A higher N is impractical for the shutter mechanism and difficult to operate. To minimize edge effects, we calculated that it is better to keep the number of blades greater than 8. For practicality and mechanical balance, we want to keep $N = 10$.

We will use an actuator motor above the pipe to adjust the radius. We hope CERN engineers and scientists can help us for further improvements of the design.

Rotor

Figure 4: Rotor with an actuator motor above it

Figure 5: Cross Section of mating rotor half, with holes for adjusting blades.

Figure 6: 3D visualization of both ends.

Figure 7: Shutter blade.

5 Experiment

To minimize the number of stray particles in our beam, we plan to use either the 0.5 – 4 GeV high-purity electron beam at CERN or the 1–6 GeV electron beam at DESY .

5.1 Detector Setup

[4]

- The beam telescope measures the incoming angle of electrons with high spatial resolution. At this stage, the beam spot is only about 2 cm in diameter, so the beam will pass within the 2×2 cm sensor area.

- 2 Timepix detectors are set before and after the tube to observe the initial and final beam profile.
- Another Halo counter is set up at a certain distance away from the tube to measure the off axis flux.
- Data from the Cherenkov detector, halo counter, and calorimeter can be used to filter events during data analysis.

5.1.1 Timepix Setup: For pure 0.5 - 6 GeV beam (low intensity flux)

- **Exposure Time:** 5 s (Reduced or increased for high or low intensity respectively)
- **Threshold Frequency:** 5 KeV (to avoid noise signals)
- **Center determination:** When an electron hits a pixel for 5 s, we will get a heatmap.
- **Chosen ROI:** Region of interest (ROI) is chosen containing the red and yellow area (20×20 px).
- **Calculating Cluster:** We will determine the cluster in ROI using python or pixel software, hence the central flux.

5.2 Experimental Methodology

5.2.1 1st Setup

To understand the intrinsic beam divergence.

Figure 8

5.2.2 2nd Setup

Keeping the tube's center aligned with the beam axis.

Figure 9

5.2.3 3rd Setup

Setting the tube's axis away from beam axis. We intend to do this by keeping the tube radius more than 6 cm to ensure the beam doesn't hit the tube wall.

Figure 10

5.2.4 4th Setup

Setting Quadrupole magnet

Figure 11

5.2.5 5th Setup

Setting up quadrupole magnets and the tube aligned with the beam axis. (As real pipe most often goes through quadrupole magnets and RF cavities, and producing a RF signal is challenging in BL4S, we want to use quadrupole magnets)

Figure 12

6 Data Analysis

Each event is analyzed particle-by-particle. Halo counter data is first used to filter out any uncollimated stray particles. Although the electron beam is highly pure, the Cherenkov detector is used to tag and filter out remaining pions or muons.

Calorimeter data is used to reject electrons which have lost > 100 MeV. These electrons may have collided with the air and changed direction or lost too much energy emitting synchrotron radiation in the quadrupole magnet or due to the effect of pipe wall.

From the remaining events, we created plots for the beam profile in different cases, using python, where we simulated the events for a perfectly round beam pipe. We want to compare these simulations with the result obtained from experiment to assess the efficiency of our design.

Figure 13: Detailed simulation results generated using a Jupyter Notebook. The left panel displays the initial beam profile, while the right panel shows the beam profile after traversing the pipe, highlighting the evolution of the beam's spatial distribution during its propagation through the system.

Figure 14: Simulation results obtained using Jupyter Notebook. The left panel displays the initial beam profile, while the right panel shows the beam profile after passing through the pipe. A deliberate offset of the beam's centroid from the pipe axis induces an image force, thereby enhancing the observable wall interaction effects.

Figure 15: Simulation results obtained via Jupyter Notebook. The left panel illustrates the initial beam profile, while the right panel presents the modified profile after the beam traverses the pipe. A quadrupole magnet positioned above the system induces anisotropic beam manipulation, focusing the beam in one plane and defocusing it in the orthogonal direction.

Figure 16: Particle tracking simulation of beam evolution under quadrupole magnet focusing and beam pipe aperture interactions. (a) Initial transverse beam cross-section at $z = 0$, displaying a symmetric Gaussian distribution. (b) Final transverse beam profile at $z = 2.0$ m, showing asymmetric particle loss and density modulations due to beam pipe aperture constraints and the quadrupole's nonlinear focusing fields. Intensity variations highlight halo formation from chromatic effects and scattering. (c) Transverse phase space (X vs. P_x), demonstrating emittance growth and nonlinear momentum-position correlations induced by fringe fields and aperture truncation. The simulation, conducted via a symplectic integrator in a Jupyter Notebook Python environment, models collective space charge dynamics and single-particle interactions with magnetic and geometric boundaries.

For the comparison to be more accurate, We would like to request CERN or DESY to provide us with a 6 cm perfectly round Beam pipe with the same characteristics.

7 What do we hope to take away from this experience:

While working as a team, we not only celebrated the joy of finding a new idea together but also shared the frustration and uncertainty of hitting rock bottom and feeling lost in equations and possibilities. Through this journey, we were exposed to advanced physics knowledge, critical thinking and determined to make at least trivial, if not big, contributions in accelerator physics. These endeavors undoubtedly enriched our technical and scientific skills which were a huge leap for us as emerging scientists. By working with the scientists and engineers of CERN and DESY, we hope to take out more valuable skills and memories that will furnish our adventure in scientific career.

8 Outreach Activity

In this three month long adventure, we found the communication gap existing between professors and high school students, making advanced physics and astronomy education and research unapproachable to most young, curious minds. The situation worsens a lot for girls [5] and distant schools.

To alleviate it, we have been in touch with science clubs throughout the country such as NDC Eco and Space Club, CTG College Physics and Astronomy Club, CZS Science Club, Paradox Physics Club, and particularly HCC Science Club and NFS Science Club, two largest girls' science clubs in Bangladesh. We plan to organize open physics, astronomy and sky gazing camps with them led by our mentors, as well as girls camp to especially encourage female students in physics and astronomy.

Furthermore, partnering with Bangladesh Olympiad on Astronomy and Astrophysics, Society for Popularization of Science and Bangladesh Physics Olympiad, we want to share our telescope with those children who gaze at the stars in the clear midnight sky in a hilly remote village and dream of traveling beyond the milky way.

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10 Appendix

Challenges

Given the mechanical nature of this design, we anticipate potential imperfections. Below, we analyze their possible impacts on beam stability and propose mitigation strategies.

1. Mechanical Gaps & Misalignment

Impact:

- Gaps or misalignments between shutter blades can locally distort the induced image charge distribution
- These discontinuities may create transverse wake fields, leading to beam deflection, emittance growth, or instability.

Mitigation:

- Thus we want to Maintain radial misalignments within tens of micrometers.

2. Surface Roughness

Impact:

- Microscopic roughness can scatter low-energy electrons and increase beam halo

Mitigation:

- Thus we need to have a polished surface.

3. Edge Effects at Blade Transitions

Impact

- Discontinuities between blades can introduce localized field enhancements
- These may cause nonlinear transverse kicks or microbunching instabilities

Mitigation:

- These effects will be minimum for N (number of blades) higher than 8. So for practicality, we choose $N = 10$.

4. Material Deformation Over Time

Impact:

- Repeated adjustments may cause deformation, resulting in misalignment and experimental drift.
- Mechanical fatigue can introduce backlash and hysteresis

Mitigation:

- Use materials with high fatigue resistance (e.g., stainless steel)

Schedule

We plan to run our experiment in about 9 days with the following schedule:

- **Day 1 - 4:** Set up experiment, align detectors, integrate the pipe.
- **Day 5:** Control run with detectors but without the pipe (to study intrinsic beam divergence).
- **Day 6:** Run with a pipe, making its center aligned with the beam axis, with different radius and energies.
- **Day 7:** Run with pipe while setting the pipe off axis with beam axis, doing the same thing as day 6.
- **Day 8:** Setting the quadrupole and running for different energies.
- **Day 9:** Setting the quadrupole and running for different pipe radius.

During the following days, we could analyze data and conduct additional runs.

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